

« Serious games », new tools to engage stakeholders

MSP challenge

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Origine and objectives

- **Serious game** : game that combines complex aspects of information, awareness, communication and teaching with the playful aspects board games. (*Michaud, 2008*)
- Developed by **Lodewijk Abspoel** (Ministry of Infrastructure and Environments), **Wander Keijser** (Rijkswaterstaat) and **Igor Mayer** (Delft University of Technology)
- Three main objectives (*Mayer, 2014*):
 - **Facilitate the understanding** of a mechanism (awareness, training)
 - **Help planning** (consultation)
 - **Promote research** and the improvement of knowledge (recommendations, data collection and information, etc.)

Methods

Utilisation context:

- Test a new method of stakeholder engagement
- Sensitizing stakeholder to the MSP through a direct application of the planning mechanisms
- National workshop of French stakeholders - October 10, 2018 in Brest.

Methods

Getting started and adaptation:

- Adaptations to **get closer to the context** and **specificities** of the French Atlantic coasts
- Shorter duration: **over only 1:30h**
- Only **7 roles** (/15) : planner, renewable energy, fisheries & aquaculture, ports & maritime industry, marine aggregates extractor, tourism and recreation, conservation managers
- 45 tokens symbolizing human activity and ecological functions (/54)
- Adding facilitators/politician (1 by country) and 1 main facilitator
- Playground only focused on ecosystem

Methods

Proceeding of the session:

- Introductory presentation
- Getting started: appropriation of the game and roles (discovery of chips, game board, etc.)
- Negotiation. Distribution of participants, according to their role, around the two negotiating tables for the achievement of supranational objectives
 - Reach 10% of marine protected areas in the coastal and marine area;
 - Initiate the ecological transition by producing 50 GW of energy thanks to renewable energies
- Discussion and game. All the players are present around the board game and negotiate the development of their own sector
- Conclusion by the planners of each country

Results

- 90% of participants recognize that **this type of tool is useful in the context of MSP** in order to understand the constraints of each sector of activity and the difficulty negotiating.
- At 80%, the participants believe that **the game is representative of the reality** even if the conflicts are strongly minimized by the convivial aspect.
- Main issues about MSP
 - the **process of stakeholder engagement** to better understand the issues of each economic sector.
 - **the environment protection** which must be considered as important as economic activities.
 - **Better cross-border cooperation**

Results

Use of this type of tool allows at :

- **Bring together stakeholders** whose interests in the MSP
- **Promotes the understanding** and the **appropriation** of the stakes of the **other sectors of activity**
- **Highlights** the importance of the **discussion** and the **stakeholders' engagement**
- Promote the **synergies** and help to **limit the conflicts**

